

DAMAGE SENSING IN FIBRE-REINFORCED COMPOSITES USING CARBON NANOTUBE NETWORKS BY SPRAY COATING

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Keywords: Carbon nanotubes, Carbon fibre, Damage sensing, Hierarchical structure

Abstract

In this paper, a novel route based on spray coating for carbon nanotube (CNTs) deposition onto fibre preforms is introduced, with good dispersion and spatial control. This spray coating technique has not only overcome traditional challenges from mixing CNTs into epoxy resin such as increased viscosity and uneven distribution, but also provides good spatial control with CNT localization in damage prone zones in fibre composite laminates. In-situ damage sensing has been performed by utilizing this deposited CNT network, and good correlation is obtained between mechanical performance and electrical sensing signals. Even for very low CNT concentrations (0.13 wt.%), the tested interlaminar fracture toughness also significantly increased by 30 % due to CNT localization at the interfacial region in the composite.

1. Introduction

The demand of using fibre-reinforced composites has significantly increased in recent years due to their outstanding mechanical properties. The increasing use of composites also raised an interest in structural health monitoring and in-service damage detection, especially for structural components for aircraft or windturbines. Apart from the excellent in-plane mechanical properties which are attributed to high-strength carbon fibres, out-of-plane properties are relatively weak which limits the performance of fibre reinforced plastics (FRPs). Various failure modes can be found in FRPs such as matrix cracking, delamination and fibre breakage [1-5]. Compared to fibre breakage which typically occurs near the end of service life, early stage failure like matrix cracking and delamination is more of a concern and it is these types of failure modes that need to be improved and monitored.

The addition of conductive fillers to insulating polymer resins has the added advantage that this will allow for the monitoring of early stage damage such as matrix cracking and delaminations. Due to the extremely good mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties of CNTs [6-10], as well as their very high aspect ratio, which can lead to a low percolation threshold, the use of CNTs into CF composites is no longer a new idea in the composites industry. Percolated CNT networks in between different layers of CF fabrics can act as damage sensing networks to detect various deformations of composites structures, such as delamination or matrix cracking [11-14]. Thostenson *et al.* [15] has shown that dispersed CNTs in an epoxy phase as distributed sensors can be used to evaluate damage onset and evolution for a specific designed mechanical test. Gao *et al.* [16] has used a sizing

agent to improve the dispersion of CNTs in epoxy resin for impact damage sensing of epoxy / glass fibre composites. However, the viscosity of epoxy resin for aerospace applications is already very high, which can impede the homogeneous dispersion of CNTs in epoxy resin. Furthermore, the filtering effects that can occur during liquid moulding manufacturing technologies such as resin transfer moulding or vacuum infusion [17], can lead to uneven CNT distribution throughout the composites, reducing the overall performance.

Therefore, there is still scope for a novel application and/or dispersion method that introduced CNTs into fibre laminates and overcomes the limitations of traditional methods. For instance, traditional methods such as where CNTs are being introduced by mixing them into resin before the subsequent composites manufacturing procedure, will lead to an increase in viscosity of the resin which interferes with composite manufacturing processes and may not only result in poor dispersion of the CNTs (without introducing any sizing or dispersing agents) and filtering effects, but have also limited control over spatial deposition.

In this work, a simple air-brushing technique for CNT dispersions is used for the deposition of CNTs onto CF fabrics, in order to introduce damage sensing capabilities to composites. Apart from its simplicity and versatility, spraying techniques are also easy to scale-up, which is very important for automated production in industries. Different parameters of air-brushing are tested with the aim to optimize the deposition and dispersion of the CNTs. The damage sensing ability of the CNT network has been characterized and correlated with different parameters depending on the deformation mode. It is also worth to mention that this method allows for creating hierarchical composite structures ranging from nano-, micro- to macro-scale and is an interesting route to optimize the use of CNTs for desired properties and applications (Fig.1).

Furthermore, the presence of CNTs near the fibre matrix interphase within the composite panels is also enhancing out-of-plane mechanical performance of CFRP composites like the resistance to delamination and other matrix dominated properties. The established in-situ damage detection approach can be utilized for in-service health monitoring of structural composite components, without the need of down-time as a result of regular inspection, solving a critical issue related to the use of advanced composites.

2. Materials and experimental procedures

2.1 Materials

Carbon nanotubes used in this work are supplied by Nanocyl S.A. (Belgium), with product no. NC7000. The carbon fibre fabrics are 2×2 twill fabrics (product no. G0986), with an areal weight of 286 g/m² and purchased from Hexcel. The two components epoxy resin RTM6-2 was also from Hexcel. Release film placed in the middle ply of the fabrics is A6000 from Aerovec. DMF used is from Sigma-Aldrich.

2.2 Airbrushing

Measured amounts of CNTs are dispersed in DMF by probe sonication, at 5000 Joules energy. Ice environment is applied throughout the sonication in the aim of avoiding any heat build-up. After sonication, the CNT solution is placed into the container of airbrushing for the spray coating processes. The airbrushing setup is an Iwata Performance plus model (H4001 HP-C PLUS), together with an Iwata studio series air compressor. The pressure for the airbrushing work is set to 30 psi (2.07 bar), with a distance of 10 cm between spray gun and carbon fabrics. Underneath the fabrics, a heating stage with carefully controlled temperature is applied in order to aid the evaporation of the solvent during the airbrushing deposition. A short evaporation time is critical in order to avoid reaggregation of the sprayed CNT network.

2.3 Vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding

Standard vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM) is used to produce composite panels in this work, with ten plies of carbon fibre fabrics and nine layers of CNTs deposited. The mould and resin is pre-heated, and the degassing process is also taken place for resin after the two parts are mixed. Infusion process is carried out under a vacuum of 1 bar at 110 °C. After the fabrics are completely infused, the mould is sealed and placed into the oven. Curing cycle at 140 °C for 1.5 hours and 180 °C for another 2 hours as post cure is applied. Release film is placed in designated areas in between fabrics, as the crack initiation point for the Mode-I test.

2.4 Mode-I test

The double cantilever beam (DCB) test is performed in order to evaluate the interlaminar fracture toughness of the produced specimens. The specimens are cut from the cured panel using a diamond saw according to the dimension requirements. Test conditions are in accordance with ASTM D5528 [18]. An Instron 5566 universal testing machine equipped with a 1 kN load cell was used for the DCB test, with the test speed being 1 mm/min. The load-displacement data and delamination crack propagation length was recorded, respectively.

2.5 In-situ damage sensing

The *in-situ* damage sensing tests are performed in conjunction with the DCB tests, using an electrical method. The open edges of the specimens are cut to expose the laminates, and to connect the electrical measurements. Silver-loaded epoxy paste is used to anchor the copper wire into the exposed ends. The volume resistance of the specimen is measured by an Agilent 34401A digit multi-metre with two probes direct current measurement throughout the test, and the data is recorded through software.

2.6 Morphology

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) is used for a morphological study of the deposition of CNTs on the fabrics before subsequent resin infusion, as well as the fracture surface of both reference and CNT deposited specimen after testing, using FEI Inspect-F model. Pictures with different magnification are taken to examine the dispersion of CNTs as well as the toughening mechanism.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Morphology

Fig. 2 shows the dispersion of the CNTs on the carbon fibre fabrics as well as the fracture surface of the tested specimen. Good dispersion of deposited CNT networks on carbon fibres can be seen from Fig. 2a after spray coating. No obvious agglomeration can be seen at the fabrics, while the fabrics are well covered by deposited CNTs.

Typical features of epoxy brittle failure can be seen from the reference specimen, as shown in Fig. 2b, with smooth fracture surfaces and exposed CFs at some areas. Fig. 2c and 2d shows the fracture surface of CNT deposited specimen, at different resolution. Very good CNT dispersion can be found at low magnification (Fig. 2c), with no obvious agglomeration. The carbon fibres are well covered by epoxy resin, with the damage prone interfacial region benefitting from the presence of CNTs. Evidence of CNT pull-out and nano-bridging is clearly shown in the fracture surface, indicating good adhesion between CNTs and epoxy resin, as well as the existence of nano-toughening mechanisms for the CNT coated CFRPs. Compared to the reference specimens, the CNT coated specimens showed more fracture features rather than the smooth fracture surface for uncoated fabrics, indicating greater energy absorption.

3.2 Interlaminar fracture toughness

Double cantilever beam (DCB) tests were performed in order to evaluate the interlaminar fracture

toughness, for both CF reference specimen as well as CNT deposited specimen. Typical load-displacement (L-D) curves of both reference and CNT deposited specimen were plotted, and are shown in Fig. 3a. It can be clearly seen that with as little as 0.13 wt.% of CNTs sprayed, the L-D curve has significantly been altered and a larger amount of energy is required during the test to initiate and propagate the crack.

The energy release rate under Mode-I (G_I) conditions was calculated according to ASTM 5528-94D standard test method, based on modified beam theory [19]. The equation is shown below:

$$G_I = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a+|\Delta|)} \quad (1)$$

Where δ is the load point displacement, P is the applied load, a is the delamination length, b is the width of the specimen, and Δ is determined experimentally by generating a least square plot of the cubic root of compliance, $C^{1/3}$, as a function of delamination length.

The relationship between toughness and crack length increment (R-curve) is also plotted, as shown in Fig. 3b. Similar to the L-D curve, a higher value for the CNT coated specimens is observed compared to the reference CF specimens, confirming the increase in interlaminar toughness. A plateau is also been found for both curves.

To directly compare the effectiveness of deposited CNTs on fracture toughness, all Mode-I results are shown in Fig. 4. For the non-linear value, which means the energy required to initiate the crack, a nearly 30 % increment is obtained with only 0.13 wt.% of CNTs. For the propagation value, an increase of 32 % is obtained, showing again a higher level of energy required to propagate the crack during interlaminar failure. All these increments are believed to be due to the good dispersion of CNTs, as well as nano-bridging effects as observed from the fractography study. To reach an effective reinforcement at such an extremely low CNT

content is also attributed to the specific CNT localization around damage prone interfacial zones using this airbrushing technique.

In previous research works, Gojny *et al.* [20] added 0.1 wt.% double-wall carbon nanotubes into epoxy resin, leading to an increased fracture toughness by 17 %. When these resins are used for the manufacturing of carbon- or glass fibre composites, the distribution of the CNTs after liquid moulding process becomes a challenge, which limits the efficiency of the CNTs in their toughening capabilities. Therefore sizing agents or functionalization might be required to overcome this challenge. In another research work of Gojny *et al.* [21], a 19 % improved fracture toughness was obtained in glass fibre reinforced composites, by using 0.1 wt.% of amino-functionalized double-wall carbon nanotubes (DWCNT-NH₂). However, both the addition of sizing agents and CNT functionalization involves several more steps during composite manufacturing, which not only add cost but also limit the ability of scale-up. Airbrushing techniques overcome this limitation by its simplicity and versatility, providing the feasibility of industrial scale-up.

3.3 In-situ damage sensing

In-situ damage sensing tests are performed together with DCB tests, using an electrical method to identify internal crack initiation and propagation status. The sensing graph is shown in Fig. 5a, showing the load-displacement curve (black) together with the measured relative electrical resistance change in percentage (red). Upon loading, an initial elastic deformation is followed by a sudden force drop due to the initiation of a crack. Then the force starts to build up again until the next crack propagation. The initial value of measured electrical resistance is maintained at a relatively stable level, and then starts to increase, accompanied with composites yielding. A resistance jump can be found to correspond with every force drop, which indicates that the internal conductive pathways have been affected by the crack opening. When the force builds

up again, the sensing signals remain at the same level until the next crack propagation. Very good correlation between each force drops and sensing signals jump can be observed, which confirms the use of internal conductive networks as a sensing tool to detect damage during mechanical deformation.

To establish a further understanding of these in-situ damage sensing properties, a correlation between each force change and resistance change is plotted and shown in Fig. 5b. The data points in the graph are extracted from the sensing graph, with only relatively large changes in order to have a more obvious comparison. It can be clearly seen that the force change and resistance change correlate very well, indicating the efficiency of this electrical method in detecting internal damage in composite laminates during mechanical deformation.

4. Conclusion

Hybrid CF / CNT composite laminates manufactured using spray coating techniques have been introduced, with engineered hierarchical structures. The introduced CNTs are located at damage prone interfacial zones to not only improve the interface dominated properties, but also establish a sensitive network for in-situ damage detection.

The deposited CNTs have shown very effective nano-reinforcements for out-of-plane properties. Concentrations as low as 0.13 wt.% have successfully increased the interlaminar fracture toughness by about 30 % for both crack initiation and propagation.

The airbrushing technique used for the application of CNTs to fibre preforms has shown its simplicity and efficiency for localized deposition of CNTs into FRPs. Furthermore, the good spatial control obtained could overcome several existing challenges related to introducing CNTs into FRPs and provide the possibility of industrial scale-up.

5. Acknowledgements

This research work is carried out under the 7th European Framework Programme (FP7) IMS & CPS project.

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Fig. 1. Hierarchical composite structure from nano-, micro- to marco-scale.

Fig. 2. SEM images of specimen: (a) CNT dispersion on CF fabrics after spray coating; (b) fracture surface of reference specimen; (c) fracture surface of CNT deposited specimen at relatively low magnification; (d) fracture surface of CNT deposited specimen at relatively high magnification.

Fig. 3. (a) The representative load-displacement curves for the DCB tests for both reference and CNT coated specimens; (b) R-curve for both reference and CNT coated fabric composites.

Fig. 4. Comparison of interlaminar fracture toughness between reference and CNT spray-coated CF fabric laminates.

Fig. 5. (a) In-situ damage sensing graph for CNT deposited specimen; (b) Sensing signal correlation between relative force- and resistivity change for CNT deposited specimen.